

Annual Report

2023

SND

Swedish National Data Service

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Preface

2023 has been another active year for SND. We have observed a trend in the increase of incoming research data, with more HEIs sharing data through SND. There has also been a rise in the number of requests for access to data.

One of SND's larger projects has been to restructure metadata in the SND research data catalogue. This means that all catalogue entries are now presented at the dataset level. By the end of 2023, the number of datasets in the SND catalogue reached 2,793.

Another significant effort has been to initiate the work on researchdata.se, aimed at Swedish researchers, where SND has established collaborations with several other research infrastructures. Four working groups are looking at various aspects of the portal's development. Simultaneously, work has begun to transform snd.se to a website tailored to the target audiences: research data support within the SND network (DAU), and the general public. Creating two separate websites will provide more clarity regarding SND's designated communities. It also follows up on the quality assessment from 2022.

SND has also participated in several external collaborations throughout the year.

The leadership of SND has undergone significant changes during 2023r. Max Petzold concluded his tenure as Director of SND at the end of June to assume the role of Deputy Vice-Chancellor for

Digitalization and Knowledge Transfer at the University of Gothenburg. In autumn, Eva Stensköld was appointed new Director of SND, and she will assume the position at the beginning of 2024. SND received a new Steering Committee and a change in governance structure, as the annual assembly was replaced by a council of stakeholders. The Steering Committee is now the highest decision-making body of SND.

Members of the SND Network have shown great commitment and enthusiasm by participating in many of the events organized by SND and, I am glad to see, in the active working groups throughout the year. Collaboration agreements with all network members have been renewed and the Swedish Geotechnical Institute and the Royal College of Music in Stockholm are new members of the SND Network.

Overall, it has been a positive year for SND, which further establishes itself as a key player in the national work on research data.

Elisabeth Strandhagen,
Acting Director of SND

SND Network

2023 has been an active year for the SND Network. SND has organized a number of events in the form of webinars, digital Q&A sessions, workshops, and in-person events. The two in-person network meetings in Gothenburg in the spring and Uppsala in the autumn were very successful and appreciated, and both gathered around 100 participants.

Several of the working groups formed during 2022 have been very active and generated valuable resources and deliverables. Staff from the SND main office have visited a majority of the member organizations of the SND Network and discussed collaborations and practical work in managing and sharing research data.

Members of the SND Network

At the end of 2023, the SND Network consisted of the following members (consortium members in bold text).

1. Blekinge Institute of Technology
2. **Chalmers University of Technology**
3. Dalarna University
4. Halmstad University
5. Jönköping University
6. Karlstad University
7. **Karolinska Institutet**
8. Kristianstad University
9. **KTH Royal Institute of Technology**
10. Linköping University
11. Linnaeus University
12. Luleå University of Technology
13. **Lund University**
14. Malmö University
15. Mid Sweden University
16. Mälardalen University
17. Swedish Veterinary Agency
18. RISE Research Institutes of Sweden
19. Royal College of Music
20. Sophiahemmet University
21. Stockholm School of Economics
22. **Stockholm University**
23. Swedish Defence University
24. Swedish Geotechnical Institute
25. Swedish Polar Research Secretariat
26. **Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences**
27. Södertörn University
28. Swedish School of Sport and Health Sciences
29. **Umeå University**
30. University College Stockholm
31. University of Borås
32. **University of Gothenburg**
33. University of Gävle
34. University of Skövde
35. University West
36. **Uppsala University**
37. Örebro University

Network activities

Full-day meetings and conferences

19
January

Introducing ERDDAP

An introduction to Environmental Research Division Data Access Program, a data server used for physical, chemical, and biological marine and atmospheric data.

2-3
May

SND network meeting in Gothenburg

Theme: Data stewards and training. Presentation of the Orienting map for open science, "Orienteringskartan", and the work to develop guiding material for sharing personal data.

6-7
November

SND network meeting in Uppsala

Theme: Disclosure of data containing personal information, managing individual data, FAIR over time.

Webinars

25
January

Challenges in managing sensitive personal information – experiences and solutions

SND domain specialists Lars Eklund and Marcus Lundberg from Uppsala University summarized their experiences in managing sensitive research data.

8
February

Outreach and training

Follow-up on the discussions from the network meeting at Karolinska Institutet in autumn 2022.

13
March

Flagship project on workflows for machine-readable data management plans

Chalmers, KTH, and SND have investigated the possibility of reusing administrative metadata when publishing datasets in DORIS.

5
April

IT forum

An opportunity for IT experts connected to the DAU operations and other research data-related activities to meet and discuss current problems and solutions.

31
May

National collaboration on business architecture and research data – what's on?

A webinar with KTH, IT Center for Science (CSC), and Örebro University that followed previous webinars on the theme of business architecture.

10
May

The Statistics Sweden online tool MONA

Focus on legal issues surrounding personal data, both during and after a research project.

31
May

Get started sharing data

Climate and environmental researchers discussed their experiences in sharing data.

Digital Q&A

About the structural changes of the SND catalogue.

Digital Q&A

About the structural changes of the SND catalogue.

Digital Q&A

About the structural changes of the SND catalogue.

Digital Q&A

About the structural changes of the SND catalogue.

Monitoring open science practices

Examples of new indicators and metrics, featuring presenters from The Charité Dashboard on Responsible Research, and Karolinska Institutet.

InfraVis and Huminfra

Research infrastructures who visualize research, research tools, and research data.

Nordic webinar series

Policy and practice in the development of open science – Norway. With speakers from the Norwegian Directorate for Higher Education and Skills, The Arctic University of Norway, and Sikt.

Digital Q&A

Digital Q&A about the Orienting Map for Open Science tool, “[Orienteringskartan](#)”.

Nordic webinar series

Policy and practice in the development of open science – Denmark. With speakers from Copenhagen Business School, DEIC, and Copenhagen University.

National collaboration on business architecture and research data – what’s on?

A webinar with KTH that follows previous webinars on the theme of business architecture.

Digital Q&A

Digital Q&A about the Orienting Map for Open Science tool, “[Orienteringskartan](#)”.

Working groups in the SND Network

In 2022, SND established several working groups with participants from a large number of HEIs in the SND network, as well as from the SND main office. Four of these have been active during 2023.

Roadmap for research data activities (“[Orienteringskartan](#)”)

This working group has developed a tool that builds on SND’s previous “Roadmap for DAU establishment” and the SUHF National Roadmap for Open Science. The result is the so-called “[Orienteringskartan](#)”, which is a practical tool to guide the HEIs on the road to open science.

Disclosure of research data containing personal information

The working group has developed a checklist for disclosing research data containing personal information. The checklist is based on SND’s guide for disclosing research data containing personal information, “[Vägledning för utlämnande av forskningsdata med personuppgifter](#)” (Guide to disclosure of research data containing personal information), and will provide practical guidance in assessing requests for disclosure at HEIs and research organizations. The working group consists of representatives from several HEIs in the SND Network, with knowledge of legal matters, archives, and libraries. The checklist is planned to be released in January 2024.

Exchange of training resources

The objective for this working group is to set the foundation for a joint introductory course on research data management for doctoral students. Several HEIs already have courses, or parts of courses, other HEIs want to get inspiration for how to create courses of their own. SND can develop a basic material that the HEIs can use and incorporate in their courses. The working group has also discussed formats and platforms for sharing training resources.

The DAU Handbook

At the beginning of the year the working group that coordinates the development of SND’s DAU Handbook presented the results of their survey about the handbook within the SND network. The survey results showed, among other things, that many people in the network would like fewer entry points to SND’s training resources. As a consequence, the plan is to migrate the contents of the DAU Handbook to the other training resources on the SND website and to set a clearer focus on the designated community. This work will be carried out in 2024.

SND Consortium

SND is governed by a consortium consisting of nine universities: University of Gothenburg, Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, KTH Royal Institute of Technology, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University. University of Gothenburg is the host university of SND, and the SND main office is in Gothenburg.

In 2023, the governance of SND has undergone changes in response to recommendations from the Swedish Resource Council. As of this year, SND's Steering Committee consists of individuals appointed based on their expertise in infrastructure and research data matters.

SND's Steering Committee has had four meetings in 2023, one of which was a residential meeting to facilitate more in-depth discussions. Their discussions have centred around SND's long-term development, strategy, and funding. The Steering Committee has also adopted a communication policy and a gender equality plan for SND.

Steering Committee

The members of the Steering Committee are:

- **Björn Halleröd**, Professor in sociology, University of Gothenburg (chair)
- **Marianne Gullberg**, Professor in psycholinguistics, Lund University
- **Sverker Holmgren**, Professor in scientific computing and Director of Chalmers e-Infrastructure Commons, Chalmers University of Technology
- **Vigdis Kvalheim**, Head of unit for research and knowledge resources, Sikt, Norway
- **Monica Lassi**, Senior data governance specialist, IKEA
- **Cecilia Martinsson Björkdahl**, Head of Compliance & Data Office, Karolinska Institutet
- **Johan Rung**, Head of SciLifeLab Data Centre, Uppsala University
- **Anders Wåhlin**, Associate professor and Director of Centre for Biomedical Engineering and Physics, Umeå University.

Starting in 2023, representatives from the nine consortium universities convene in a council of stakeholders, which will serve as an advisory body to the Steering Committee in connection to the application for renewed funding from the Swedish Research Council. They will also provide advice if the Steering Committee wishes to implement strategic or financial measures that affect the consortium universities' in-kind commitments during the current funding period.

Flagships

There have been four Flagship projects during the year, run by members of the SND consortium. A Flagship is a comprehensive project, but limited in time, to develop routines, knowledge, and technology for research data management or data sharing, where a clearly stated goal is that other HEIs shall be able to benefit from the results.

Chalmers and KTH:

Efficient reuse of administrative research information from project initiation to data publication

The project is an independent continuation of the flagship pilot conducted by Chalmers and KTH in collaboration with SND. The goal is to reduce the administrative burden on researchers by reusing information about research projects through machine-readable data management plans that communicate with other research administrative systems. The project aims to develop a solution to create and fill out a data management plan using metadata from other systems, such as SweCris. One major benefit of the initiative is that researchers and research administrators can avoid having to manually enter the same information into multiple systems.

Karolinska Institutet:

KI Data Repository – Phase 1: Interim solution for local storage without integration with DORIS

This is a two-phase project to create a solution where researchers at KI can securely and in a structured way store sensitive data and make them accessible through the SND catalogue. In the first phase (the flagship project), this is done manually via the interim solution for local storage without integration with SND (DORIS). Phase two will involve creating a permanent local storage solution with an integration between the university storage and DORIS. The storage issue is a central part of the universities' work to make research data accessible. The results from KI's project can demonstrate how to create functional storage systems before a final integrated data storage is in place.

Lund University:

Preserved and accessible databases

This project aims to develop a process to make actively used databases simultaneously accessible and preserved for long-term storage. An inventory conducted at the university revealed that researchers need to safeguard the operation and maintenance of databases over a longer time, especially after the project ends, when funding is uncertain. The flagship project primarily targets researchers in the humanities and social sciences, but the results can be applied in other scientific fields. Questions about responsibility, operations, and costs for the preservation of research data are relevant for all Swedish HEIs. This flagship project can show how to work towards creating long-term technical systems and solutions for preserving databases.

Stockholm University:

Certification of the Bolin Centre Database – a repository for climate, environmental, and earth system data at Stockholm University

The goal for this project is to make the Bolin Centre Database a CoreTrustSeal certified repository. The database already meets several of the certification requirements, but not all. By integrating the database into the university's central research support, functions such as IT support, data curation, legal support, and e-archives will become more accessible to the repository and contribute to its development towards a more sustainable organization. One of the long-term goals of SND's collaborations is to create certified repositories at the HEIs in the network. The certification of Bolin Centre can serve as an example of how the process can proceed, and experiences from the project can be used to facilitate future certification initiatives.

Internal projects

Changing the structure of metadata

In June 2023, SND launched extensive changes to its research data catalogue and its publication tool DORIS. The purpose of these changes was to make it easier to find and share data through SND and to improve the user experience. The changes also mean that the SND research data catalogue is better adapted to global standards, which facilitates the visibility of Swedish research data internationally.

Before the structural change, research data were described on two levels: data description (formerly called study) and dataset. A metadata element usually appeared at only one level, but some elements, such as title, description, keywords, and time period, could appear at both levels. This structure was complex and problematic to make work, both technically and communicatively. It was complicated for those entering or reviewing the metadata, and difficult to overview for those visiting the catalogue entries. This was also pointed out by the external SND Quality Investigation 2022. A simpler model would also facilitate the development of new services, for example researchdata.se and export/import from other systems.

The structural change mainly affected data descriptions that contained more than one dataset. These datasets were either separated into several data descriptions or merged into one single dataset with one data description. Metadata that were previously common for several datasets are now included in each data description and the datasets are clearly linked to each other. In some cases, the datasets within a data description are merged to form a new combined dataset. SND ensures that relevant

metadata accompany the new merged dataset, and that existing DOIs will redirect to the new dataset. In addition, SND reviews the need for other types of relationships between datasets and how they can be best presented in the catalogue entries. This work is still ongoing.

After the structural change, the most noticeable difference for users of the SND research data catalogue is that the search results are now displayed per dataset. The landing pages for data descriptions have received an updated layout that provides a better overview of the data and metadata on a single page. This helps users quickly find the right information. Several new features have been introduced to improve the user experience. Among other things, it has become easier to navigate between different versions of datasets, and for data stored at SND it is now possible to download all files relating to a dataset as a zip file. Other improvements include previewing image files, listing files in zip files, downloading metadata as a PDF file, and the ability to download an overview of all files in a catalogue entry in CSV format.

For who share sharing data through SND's publishing tool, DORIS, the interface has been updated and simplified to focus more clearly on data and documentation files. DORIS has received an expanded detail view with new activity history entries and notifications that facilitate the process for reviewing and publishing datasets. Researchers can now also update metadata for published datasets directly without review.

Collaboration with Sunet

The collaboration with Sunet on the development of the technical integration between SND DORIS and Sunet Drive has continued during 2023. The integration will allow data stored in Sunet Drive to be published in SND DORIS without transferring data from Sunet Drive.

The integration relies on Sciebo-RDS, a third-party plugin to NextCloud, which is the web interface that Sunet Drive is based on. SND's efforts are directed towards developing a connector module which communicates with Sciebo-RDS to transfer file level metadata about the dataset to SND DORIS so that a data description can be published in the SND research data catalogue. The integration will allow for both sensitive and non-sensitive data.

A first version of the integration was planned for testing in August. This test launch was cancelled due to problems setting up a functioning development environment, which caused the development to be delayed.

Another launch was planned for testing together with Stockholm University in November/December, but this was again delayed due to problems with setting up a functioning environment. Both these delays are due to the complexity and some stability issues with the Sciebo-RDS plugin.

Communication policy

In 2023, SND adopted a communication policy for the years 2023–2026, based on SND's strategic plan for the same period. The policy covers both internal and external communication, and describes basic principles, overall messages, target groups and communication channels.

In addition to the communication policy, there are complementary documents that regulate and describe SND's communication activities. Some of these are the annual operational and communication plans and the separate plans that describe specific communication activities related to major development projects.

Gender equality plan

SND's goal is to achieve an equal workplace by increasing awareness of gender equality issues and improving equal opportunities within the organization. In 2023, SND adopted our first gender equality plan for the years 2024–2026.

The efforts to achieve gender equality take place on an annual basis and follow four main phases: mapping of current conditions; analysis of discovered risks and obstacles; actions that include prevention and equality promotion; and follow-up and evaluation, which lays the foundation for next year's gender equality plan.

The activities in the gender equality plan for 2024 concern, for example, leadership, decision-making, recruitment, career opportunities, and work-life balance. The work to produce the plan was conducted by a smaller group with expertise in the field, but staff and management at SND were also involved at various stages during the process.

Researchdata.se

Researchdata.se is a collaborative effort to create a new national platform for finding and accessing research data and training materials on research data management. During spring 2023, a project plan was formulated and later approved by the SND leadership team.

A call for expression of interest was sent to a number of research infrastructures with established facilities for sharing data and/or education and training resources for research data management to join the development of researchdata.se. Participating infrastructures, other than SND, during the development phase will be Bolin Centre, Huminfra, InfraVis, NBIS, SBDI/GBIF, SciLifeLab, SITES, and Swedigarch.

The project formally started with a joint meeting in August 2023 with representatives from the

participating infrastructures. During autumn, four working groups with representatives from both SND and the other infrastructures have started working on the project and have drafted their own plans and priorities. These working groups will focus on different aspects of researchdata.se: Sharing data; Metadata and harvesting; Education and training; and Design, communication, and outreach. These groups will be coordinated by a project management group.

The researchdata.se platform will host research data and resources for research data management contributed by the project partners and will be a national portal primarily for Swedish researchers. SND's contributions to researchdata.se include the research data catalogue and our popular "Manage data" web pages that contain tips on how to make and maintain research data accessible.

Restructuring snd.se

The transfer of the "Manage data" web pages to researchdata.se will be used as an opportunity to systematically consolidate and update our web resources. In late 2023, SND finalized a migration plan that utilizes an internal review process and addresses legacy issues identified by the external SND Quality Investigation 2022.

The transfer of resources to researchdata.se and associated restructure will result in two different portals. In addition to researchdata.se, the site snd.se will feature content primarily for research support personnel, including staff at universities, other infrastructures, and funders. The language in both portals will be adapted to be accessible to a wider audience according to the principles of plain language (klarspråk). Development of researchdata.se and snd.se will continue during 2024 with a planned launch during the first quarter of 2025.

Training activities

SND's increased emphasis on training activities took several forms in 2023, with the most visible being the initiatives "SND pratar på plats" and the workshop programs organized back-to-back with the in-person SND network meetings.

"SND pratar på plats" is an offer for SND staff to visit member organizations in the SND Network and speak directly to researchers and doctoral students. The content is flexible and adjusted according to the needs identified by the organization's DAU. In response to the initiative announcement, SND visited at Karlstad University, Dalarna University, Umeå University, and Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, with an additional virtual

presentation for the Icelandic Open Access Week, hosted by the libraries at the University of Akureyri and Bifröst University.

SND continued to coordinate parallel training workshops in connection to the in-person SND network meetings in Gothenburg in May and in Uppsala in November. In addition to workshops led by staff from the SND head office, training was provided by domain specialists Karina Nilsson (Umeå University), Anna Axmon (Lund University), Lars Eklund (Uppsala University), Marcus Lundberg (Uppsala University), and also Yvonne Kallberg (NBIS/ SciLifeLab).

Finally, 2023 saw a return to in-person learning for the training course "Forskningsdata: tillgänglighet, hantering och samverkan", run by University of Borås in collaboration with SND. Both teachers and participants appreciated that "Forskningsdata: THS" is more than just a training course in data management; it is also a wonderful opportunity to get to know staff from the SND Network!

National collaboration

National open science guidelines

At the request of the Swedish government, The National Library of Sweden (KB) have developed national guidelines for open science. The guidelines are intended to support and guide the Swedish actors involved in the transition to open science, and with the development of national guidelines, Sweden is now in line with UNESCO's recommendations. SND has been part of the reference group supporting the National Library in developing the guidelines.

SUHF

The Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF) brings Sweden's universities and higher education institutions together in a collective arena for discussions, collaboration and action on issues of common interest. SND is represented in both SUHF's group for coordination of open science and their research data group.

Dataportal.se

The Agency for Digital Government (DIGG) operates Sweden's data portal, dataportal.se, which makes it possible to search for data from both public and private institutions in Sweden. During 2023, SND has collaborated with DIGG, making data and metadata from the SND catalogue visible and searchable in dataportal.se.

Swedish Government Official Reports (SOU)

Recent collaboration, established during the year, saw SOU share data from one of the government's official reports via SND.

DiVA

Academic Archive Online (DiVA) is a collaborative search engine and an open archive for research publications from a number of Swedish higher education institutions. During the year, SND initiated discussions with DiVA regarding the collaborative publication of research data.

International collaboration

SND is part of a global network of research data infrastructures, where collaboration has a central role. SND's international collaborations fall into two main categories: initiatives from the European Union, such as EOSC and CESSDA ERIC, and organizations that provide essential services or expertise related to research data management and repositories.

EOSC

The ambition of the [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#) is to provide European researchers, innovators, companies, and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation, and educational purposes.

The [EOSC Association](#) is the legal entity established to govern EOSC. It was formed in 2020 and now has more than 250 members and observers. SND, with the University of Gothenburg as host university, is a member, as well as ten other Swedish organizations, seven of which are SND consortium universities.

CESSDA ERIC

The [Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives \(CESSDA\)](#) is an ERIC, a European Research Infrastructure Consortium, which provides large-scale, integrated, and sustainable data services to the social sciences. It brings together social science data archives across Europe with the aim of promoting the results of social science research and supporting national and international research and cooperation. Sweden is a member of CESSDA ERIC and SND is appointed Swedish Service Provider.

ARIADNE RI

The [ARIADNE Research Infrastructure](#) was founded in November 2022 and SND became a member in 2023. It is a not-for-profit association that will continue the work from the ARIADNEplus project. ARIADNE RI will work to ensure that the ARIADNE portal is maintained, which will enable the update of existing datasets, and the addition of new members and new datasets. It has a broad membership and represents the largest international grouping of archaeological data repositories, national heritage bodies, museums, scientific research organizations, and universities. It brings together archaeologists and information scientists in a collaboration that enables them to apply for international research funding as a single legal entity.

RDA 20th Plenary/RDA Sweden

In commemoration of the first RDA meeting in Gothenburg ten years ago, the RDA 20th Plenary with the theme "A Decade of Data: Celebrating 10 Years of the Research Data Alliance" was hosted in Gothenburg, co-organized by SND and Chalmers University of Technology. The conference took place from 21–23 March at Lindholmen Conference Centre and attracted some 500 attendees on-site and a smaller number remotely.

SND initiated a session on quality indicators for data publications. Publishing research data as standalone data publications is not a common practice for all researchers. To encourage this, there is a need for incentive structures where high-quality publications of research data are considered in research assessments. However, the lack of information and consensus on what is important to evaluate makes it challenging to establish such practices.

Following initial discussions at the IASSIST 2022 conference, a collaboration started between representatives from SND, Stockholm University, University of Gothenburg, Karolinska Institutet,

and the publisher Elsevier. The goal was to examine quality indicators for data publications and infrastructure support in a Swedish context, aligning with the national objective for a transition to open access to research data by 2026. During the RDA conference, a preliminary draft was presented, which outlines a framework for measurable quality indicators.

Additionally, at the RDA 20th Plenary, new discussions began on how the Swedish national node of RDA, which has not been very active, can be utilized as a channel for further collaborations and outreach in Sweden.

Projects

Skills4EOSC, a three-year project funded by Horizon Europe, was launched in September 2022. The project brings together expertise from national, regional, institutional, and thematic Open Science and Data Competence Centres from 18 European countries. The goal of the project is to unify the current training landscape into a common and trusted pan-European ecosystem in order to accelerate the upskilling of European researchers and data professionals in the field of FAIR and Open Data, intensive-data science, and scientific data management.

SND leads Work Package 8, “Synergies, stakeholder engagement, advocacy, and communications”, and takes part in several other work packages and tasks. Other Swedish participants and affiliated entities are Chalmers University of Technology, Karolinska Institutet, and Umeå University.

SND also participates in one of the science projects in **EOSC Future: Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities**. It demonstrates how relevant environmental data and data on citizens’ values, attitudes, behaviours, and involvement can be combined for social, political, and scientific analysis.

SND participated in the Cost Action project **SEADDA** (Saving European Archaeology from the Digital Dark Age). The project brought together an interdisciplinary network of archaeologists and computer scientists to create publications and materials to set a state-of-the-art standard for archaeological archiving across Europe. The project was completed in autumn 2023.

Applications for new projects

SND, together with 28 other partners connected to a consortium of four major research infrastructures, applied for EU funding for the project **ATRIUM** (Advancing frontTier Research In the arts and hUManities). In July 2023, it was announced that funding had been granted and that the project will begin in January 2024.

ATRIUM will utilize and strengthen complementarities between leading European infrastructures in the Arts and Humanities domain – DARIAH, ARIADNE, CLARIN and OPERAS – to facilitate access to a rich portfolio of state-of-the-art services for arts and humanities scholars across countries, languages, domains, and media. It builds on a shared understanding and interoperability principles established in the SSHOC cluster project, and other previous collaborations.

OSTrails (Open Science Trails) is a three-year EU-funded project to assist researchers in making their research more accessible and reusable (FAIR). The project, which begins in February 2024, is led by the OpenAIRE organization, and a part of the EOSC collaboration. SND participates in OS Trails along with 37 partners from 15 EU countries. SND’s role will be to conduct a national pilot study to evaluate the methods and products developed within the project.

SHADE (Sharing Heritage and Archaeological Data Effectively) is a one-year project funded by a COST Innovation Grant. The project is a continuation of SEADDA, with the goal to develop a more permanent way of financing the continued operations of ARIADNE RI.

Statistics

The SND Research Data Catalogue has 2,818 searchable entries, which have been added since 1982. 127 new entries were added in 2023.

Users

SND has 3,220 registered users. There were 674 new registered users in 2023.

Catalogue page views

There were 111,473 views (or 93,640 unique views) of catalogue pages during 2023.

Downloaded material

Many studies in the SND catalogue are freely accessible to download. There were in total 43,140 direct downloads¹ from the SND catalogue in 2023.

Data requests

Many datasets that are not accessible by direct download can be requested from the SND catalogue. In 2023, SND received 473 requests, resulting in the dissemination of 1,160 datasets.²

Collections

Datasets that form part of a collection or series are among the most popular requests. The two series with the greatest number of data requests in 2023 were the Swedish National Election Studies and the National Society Opinion Media (SOM) surveys. Swedish Electoral Data and the SVT Exit Poll Surveys were also popular.

Data access level	Downloads
Access to data through SND – Data are freely accessible	22,801
Access to data through SND – Access to data is restricted/Data are accessible by order	14,455 (documentation only)
Access to data through an external actor	5,884 (documentation only)
TOTAL	43,140

¹ Total number of downloads. Some downloads are comprised of several files. Attempts have been made to identify and remove automatic downloads by, for example, bots. It is, however, unlikely that they have been eliminated completely from the statistics.

² A number of popular SOM Surveys were not available during 2023. This has affected the number of datasets disseminated.

Top 3 downloads

1

ACROBAT - a multi-stain breast cancer histological whole-slide-image data set from routine diagnostics for computational pathology.

2,185 downloads

2

Dataset for SOU 2023:18 The Wind's Value - Compensation, Incentives and Planning for a Continued Sustainable Wind Power Development

1,462 downloads

3

The DREAM Dataset: Behavioural data from robot enhanced therapies for children with autism spectrum disorder.

695 downloads

Top 3 requested collections

1

Swedish Election Studies - Parliamentary Elections

391 dataset requests

2

The National SOM Survey

365 dataset requests

3

Swedish Electoral Data

181 dataset requests

Number of catalogue posts 1982–2023

During 2023, the SND catalogue was restructured to focus on datasets rather than studies with one or more datasets. This change has been applied retroactively to the years prior to 2023 in the chart.

Economy

Statement of financial performance for 2023

REVENUE	Results 2023	Budget 2023
Government grants	8,075	8,075
Revenue from services in the SND Network	1,775	1,690
Other sales	2	0
Co-funding of externally funded research	65	0
External research funding	20,579	20,050
Salary cost compensation from the SND Consortium	12,000	12,000
Exchange rate gains	1	0
Accruals	-840	0
Depreciation coverage of grant-funded facilities	26	0
Total revenue	41,683	41,815
EXPENSES		
Salary costs	-19,352	-21,475
Salary costs for the SND Consortium	-12,000	-12,000
Holiday pay costs	-126	0
Travel and representation expenses	-410	-730
Purchase of services	-341	-320
Other staff costs	-348	-660
Other operating costs	-1,451	-1,445
University overhead costs	-2,960	-2,940
Co-funding of externally funded research	-24	0
Premises	-1,402	-1,285
Exchange rate losses	-4	0
Depreciation	-37	-40
Total expenses	-38,455	-40,895
Deficit/surplus for 2023	3,228	920
Opening balance 2023	4,202	
Ending balance 2023	7,430	

Figures stated in thousand SEK

Staff

SND office

Senior Advisor
Iris Alfredsson

Research Data
Advisor
Eira Brandby

Research Data
Advisor
Joel Carlsten
Rosberg

System Developer
Alireza Davoudian

Financial Officer
Anna Maria
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Developer
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University of
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Sciences

Ylva Toljander
Swedish
University of
Agricultural
Sciences

Without picture:
IT Technician Alicia Rain Olsbänning

As well as Elisabeth Strandhagen and Iris Alfredsson, who are Domain Specialists at University of Gothenburg.

Swedish National Data Service (SND)

Is a research infrastructure that promotes increased open access to research data.

Together with a network of Swedish universities and research institutes, SND supports researchers in making data accessible for reuse.

Visit snd.se/en to learn more.

SND

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